

Professor Pulin Behari Sarkar A personal appreciation

N. R. Dhar

Professor P. B. Sarkar, a distinguished inorganic chemist, passed away a few months ago.

I had the pleasure of teaching him elementary physical chemistry from July 1909 when he joined the Presidency College, Calcutta, and resided in the Hindu Hostel. Since that time I was closely associated with him and the members of his family. He was born in Tamruk, Midnapore and I visited his birth place and met his father, who was a lawyer there, and his maternal grandfather, who also was a very able man and lawyer and Dr. Sarkar's mother inherited many good qualities from him.

After passing his B.Sc. (Honours) examination in 1913, Prof. Sarkar started systematic research work under my guidance on manganese dioxide and manganites. These researches were embodied in several papers published mostly in Germany and have been largely quoted in standard books by Mellor, Friend, Pascal and others.

Prof. Sarkar was anxious to study in Europe and I got him admitted under my teacher, *late* Professor Georges Urbain, a great leader in rare earth chemistry and an eminent Professor in the University of Sorbonne at Paris. When Dr. Sarkar was working under Prof. Urbain, I visited him in 1926 and I was pleased to find that Professor Urbain was very favourably impressed by the ability and excellent skill, and accuracy in analysis shown by Dr. Sarkar. Prof. Urbain was deeply interested not only in the rare earth chemistry in which he was a great authority but also in many physicochemical problems and he specially studied and emphasised his ideas on the problem of similitude of elements and their compounds and studied the problems in a very systematic way and delivered lectures in the Sorbonne. His aim was to systematise precisely our knowledge in the inorganic substances.

Professor Sarkar followed the footsteps of his teacher and was deeply interested in the same problem. This was evident in his university lectures.

The great merit of Professor Sarkar was his superb skill and precision in the most difficult analytical work. He could estimate accurately not only the common substances but could also handle newly discovered elements like hafnium, rhenium, etc., existing in the minerals and studied many compounds of elements found in small amounts in the earth's crust.

For his ability and efficiency in physical and inorganic chemistry, Professor Sarkar was appointed first a lecturer and then Ghosh Professor of Chemistry in the University of Calcutta.

In 1923 when Professor M. N. Saha was appointed University Professor of Physics in the University of Allahabad at my initiative, I was anxious to have Dr. P. B. Sarkar also as the first lecturer in analytical chemistry in this university. But Dr. Sarkar went abroad shortly afterwards to join the University of Paris.

Professor Sarkar was respected by his colleagues and his students, and was one of the early presidents of the chemistry section of the Indian Science Congress Association. He was also a founder member of the Indian Chemical Society, member of the council and a Vice-President.

Dr. P. B. Sarkar was a very fine man, simple in outlook and habits, but, had great idealism and was honest, straightforward and devoted to his duties. He did everything possible to push his students and guide them on proper lines.

For several years from 1909, Dr. Sarkar, Dr. M. N. Saha, Sir J. C. Ghosh, Dr. J. N. Mukherji (who is happily with us) and Surendra Prasad Roy, a brilliant chemist, were constantly together with me under the leadership of my GURU, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, and all of us spent many summer vacations together in Karmatar, Madhupur and other places. Also the same group was a constant visitor to our Jessore house when my *late* brother, Dr. J. R. Dhar, Minister of Public Health, West Bengal, was with us. We also formed the 'Maidan group' (Eden Garden) of Acharya P. C. Ray.

Professor Sarkar was robust in his early days and played tennis and other games vigorously, but, later on, his constant trouble was a leaking kidney, which made him to take good care of himself.

Professor Pulin Behari Sarkar will be remembered not only for his contributions in chemistry but also as a kind and lovable teacher and a friend to many of his students and colleagues.